

A nearly-conservative, high-order, forward Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of scalar hyperbolic conservation laws

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Abstract

In this work, we present a novel Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of scalar hyperbolic conservation laws. The scheme considers: (i) a conservative, weak, Lagrangian formulation which is formally discretized in space and in time with arbitrary order of accuracy, (ii) a forward-in-time integration of the fluid trajectories to allow for more stable and efficient time discretizations, (iii) nodal space-discretizations on unstructured triangular meshes and (iv) a novel and simple operator which employs the values of the fine-scale term of the solution to detect and capture the discontinuities. The method has been tested on several benchmark problems –including a hard case of non-convex flux– using a third-order time-integration formula and up to fourth-order finite elements, yielding the expected convergence rates both for smooth and discontinuous solutions. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first Lagrange–Galerkin method for hyperbolic conservation laws in the literature that allows for discontinuous solutions.

Keywords: Lagrange–Galerkin method, finite element method, hyperbolic conservation laws, discontinuity-capturing, high-order methods, triangular meshes

1. Introduction

In the last decades, a great effort has been done on the development of finite element codes for the resolution of hyperbolic conservation laws due to their presence in many fields of science, such as aerodynamics [1], combustion [2] and polymers [3]. For instance, we can distinguish discontinuous Galerkin algorithms [4], Petrov-Galerkin methods [5, 6], pure Lagrangian schemes [7–11], arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) methods [12, 13], semi-Lagrangian methods [11, 14–20] and Lagrange–Galerkin algorithms [21–25].

In both semi-Lagrangian and Lagrange–Galerkin methods, the material derivatives are discretized (typically) backward-in-time along the flow trajectories. In this way, they achieve the following advantages [22, 26]: (i) the convective terms in the equations are stabilized in a natural and straightforward way, (ii) the systems to be solved are linear and have symmetric matrices and (iii) mesh distortion problems are avoided. For that purpose, the numerical information of some of the previously computed solutions has to be transferred from the background reference mesh to a backward-in-time displaced mesh. This step is more accurate in Lagrange–Galerkin methods than in semi-Lagrangian methods, as it is done in terms of L^2 projections and not by interpolations [23].

Lagrange–Galerkin methods have been successfully applied to many nonlinear problems such as the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations [21, 22, 27, 28], the shallow water equations [29, 30] and combustion [23, 31]. However, as far as we know, none of the Lagrange–Galerkin methods available in the literature takes

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into account for possible discontinuities in the solution. This drawback has motivated the consideration in this work of a novel Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of scalar hyperbolic conservation laws with discontinuous solutions. The method is an extension of a previous work [32] which considered linear conservation laws and smooth solutions, and is characterized by the features explained next.

First, unlike conventional Lagrange–Galerkin methods, it is mass-conservative, which is of huge importance to accurately capture and track the discontinuities in the solution. For that purpose, we adopt the so-called *weak Lagrange–Galerkin* formulation [33] developed by Benqué et al. [27, 34] and employed later by Giraldo [25, 29], Kaazempur-Mofrad et al. [35, 36] and Colera et al. [32], which achieves mass-conservation by enforcing that the weighting functions be constant along the trajectories of the fluid particles. Note that this formulation is somehow similar to that of some versions of the Eulerian–Lagrangian localized adjoint method (ELLAM) [37, 38], although reads much simpler as it manipulates some terms (mainly those due to the boundary conditions) in a different way.

Secondly, the discretization of the flow trajectories in semi-Lagrangian and Lagrange–Galerkin methods is normally backward-in-time, that is, the trajectories are computed from an unsolved time t^{n+1} to the last solved time t^n . To do so, one needs to extrapolate the velocity field from previous solutions [25, 39, 40] and/or to employ implicit or predictor-corrector schemes [17]. This strategy makes high-order methods difficult to implement and expensive [17]. To solve this problem, we integrate the flow trajectories forward-in-time in an explicit fashion with a high-order Runge–Kutta method. This approach has already been employed in some semi-Lagrangian methods [17, 20, 41, 42] and is standard in ALE formulations; however, it seems to have received little attention in the context of Lagrange–Galerkin methods.

Furthermore, we consider nodal high-order space-discretizations on unstructured triangular meshes. As pointed by some authors [8, 10, 30], triangular meshes are more amenable for automatic mesh generation and remeshing than quadrilateral ones, and also allow for an easier coupling with state-of-the-art codes developed for electromagnetism, transport radiation problems and other physics. In addition, high-order discretizations are able to capture shocks within a smaller number of elements [43] and have better scaling properties in the case of parallel computations [44]. It must be noted that very few works in the literature [8, 10, 12] deal at the same time with discontinuities, high-order discretizations and unstructured triangular meshes.

Finally, as it is well-known, to avoid numerical instabilities provoked by the discontinuities in the solution, one needs to employ techniques such as adding artificial diffusion at the vicinities of the discontinuities [9, 13, 43, 45, 46] or using level-set functions [47, 48]. In this text, we also develop a novel and simple discontinuity-capturing operator of artificial-diffusion type, which detects the discontinuity by post-processing the fine-scale term of a previously computed non-stabilized solution.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the weak formulation for the continuous problem and explains its numerical discretization. In Section 3, some numerical experiments are performed to address the accuracy and efficiency of the new method. Finally, the conclusions and some possible future works are discussed in Section 4.

2. Formulation and discretization

2.1. Weak formulation of the continuous problem

In this work, we focus on conservation equations of the form

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{a}u) = 0, \quad (1)$$

with $u = u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ a scalar quantity, \mathbf{a} the velocity field, \mathbf{x} the position vector and t the time. For convenience, we consider that \mathbf{a} describes the motion of a fluid, although in reality it may govern the motion of any kind of continuum. The velocity field can either be prescribed as a function $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ or be given in terms of the unknown u as $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(u)$. As it is well known, in the latter case the solution of Eq. (1) may turn discontinuous even if the initial condition is smooth –consider, e.g., the Burger’s equation. Note that any equation of the form

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{f}(u) = 0,$$

84 with $\mathbf{f}(u)$ a non-singular flux, can be rewritten as (1) by considering a non-singular velocity field $\mathbf{a}(u) =$
 85 $(\mathbf{f}(u) - \mathbf{f}(0))/u$.

86 The conservative, weak formulation associated with (1) reads as follows. Let $\Omega_f = \Omega_f(t)$ be an arbitrary
 87 domain that moves with the velocity field \mathbf{a} –that is, a *fluid domain*–, and $v = v(\mathbf{x}, t)$ a continuous test
 88 function that remains constant along the trajectories of the fluid particles –that is, $Dv/Dt := \partial v/\partial t + \mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla v = 0$.
 89 Then [25, 32],

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega_f(t)} uv \, d\Omega = 0, \quad (2)$$

90 which can be interpreted from a physical point of view as a conservation law for the *weighted mass*. Note
 91 that the law of standard mass conservation is a particular case of (2) in which $v \equiv 1$.

92 2.2. Space discretization

93 The space discretization employed here is similar to that detailed in our previous work [32], and is
 94 reviewed next for the sake of completeness.

95 Hereafter, we assume that Eq. (1) is to be solved at a fixed, two-dimensional, polygonal domain Ω_h . We
 96 begin the space discretization by considering a fixed, admissible decomposition \mathbb{T}_h of Ω_h into isoparametric
 97 triangles, in which the nodes are distributed according to a Chebyshev grid of the second kind [49] to allow
 98 for stable high-order discretizations. The finite element space associated with \mathbb{T}_h is $V_h = P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\mathbb{T}_h) :=$
 99 $P_r(\mathbb{T}_h) \oplus B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$, where r is the desired order for the space discretization, $P_r(\mathbb{T}_h)$ is the well-known space
 100 of polynomials of maximal degree r , and $B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ is the part of the space spanned by the products of the
 101 standard bubble function with the basis functions of $P_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ that is not already contained in P_r . Recall
 102 that the functions in $B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ cancel at the edges of the elements. Thus, each function $v_h \in V_h$ can be
 103 expressed as the sum

$$v_h = \bar{v}_h + v_h', \quad (3)$$

104 of a *large-scale* term, $\bar{v}_h \in P_r(\mathbb{T}_h)$, and a *fine-scale* term, $v_h' \in B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$. This decomposition is done with
 105 the purpose of employing subgrid stabilization techniques [22, 50–52] as well as the discontinuity-capturing
 106 operator developed later.

107 In addition, we define the *convected mesh* $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$ as the one that results from displacing \mathbb{T}_h from a given
 108 reference time t^n to a generic time $t \geq t^n$. More precisely, let us assume for the moment that the trajectories
 109 $\chi_i(t)$ of the N_h nodes $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^{N_h}$ of the mesh \mathbb{T}_h are known. It is clear that, for each element $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$, we can
 110 define an isoparametric *convected element* $\tilde{K}_h(t)$ from the convected nodes of K . That is, K and $\tilde{K}_h(t)$ are
 111 respectively the images of the isoparametric transformations

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_K : \bar{\mathbf{x}} \in \widehat{K} &\longrightarrow \mathbf{x} \in K, & \mathbf{x} &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_v} \mathbf{x}_{n_i} \widehat{L}_i(\bar{\mathbf{x}}), \\ \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K : \bar{\mathbf{x}} \in \widehat{K}, t \in [t^n, \infty) &\longrightarrow \mathbf{x} \in \tilde{K}_h(t), & \mathbf{x} &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_v} \chi_{n_i}(t) \widehat{L}_i(\bar{\mathbf{x}}), \end{aligned}$$

112 with \widehat{K} the well-known reference triangle, N_v the number of nodes of the element, n_i the i -th local node
 113 of K and $\widehat{L}_i(\bar{\mathbf{x}})$ the Lagrange polynomial associated with the i -th node of \widehat{K} . Then, $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t) := \cup_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} \tilde{K}_h(t)$.
 114 Note that the convected mesh is a decomposition of the *convected domain*

$$\tilde{\Omega}_h(t) := \{ \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^2 : \mathbf{x} = \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, t), \bar{\mathbf{x}} \in \widehat{K}, \tilde{K}_h(t) \in \tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t) \}.$$

115 Finally, we define the *convected finite element space* $\tilde{V}_h(t)$ as that spanned by the functions in V_h when they
 116 are transported along the fluid trajectories from t^n to t , i.e.,

$$\tilde{V}_h(t) = \left\{ v_h(\mathbf{x}, t) : \frac{Dv_h}{Dt} = 0, v_h(\mathbf{x}, t^n) \in V_h \right\}.$$

117 Now we make two assumptions. First, the time step $t - t^n$ is small enough so that the elements of $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$
 118 are not distorted. To check that a triangle $\tilde{K}_h(t)$ is not distorted, we can proceed as in [53] or verify that

119 $\det(\partial \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}, t)/\partial \tilde{\mathbf{x}}) > 0$ in a set of points inside the triangle¹. Secondly, let $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t)$ denote the (exact)
 120 position at time t of the fluid particle that occupies the position \mathbf{x} at time t^n , and let $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$ be the element
 121 that contains \mathbf{x} . Then,

$$\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t) \simeq \mathbf{X}_h(\mathbf{x}, t) := \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K(\mathbf{F}_K^{-1}(\mathbf{x}), t). \quad (4)$$

122 That is, $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t)$ is approximated by the point on $\tilde{K}_h(t)$ that is defined by the same natural coordinates
 123 on \tilde{K} than \mathbf{x} [23, 54]. See also Fig. 1.

124 Finally, let us consider a function $v_h(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \tilde{V}_h(t)$. Since v_h is constant along the fluid trajectories, we
 125 have $v_h(\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t), t) = v_h(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$. In that case, assumption (4) yields

$$v_h|_{\tilde{K}_h(t)}(\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}, t), t) = v_h|_K(\mathbf{F}_K(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}, t^n)), \quad \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h.$$

126 That is, v_h reads always the same when expressed in terms of natural coordinates in the reference element,
 127 irrespective of t . The latter also implies that $\tilde{V}_h(t)$ is a P_r^{bubble} space associated with the convected mesh
 128 $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$, i.e., $\tilde{V}_h = P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h)$. In addition, when $v_h(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ is the i -th shape function of V_h , then $v_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is
 129 the i -th shape function of $\tilde{V}_h(t)$ and vice versa.

Figure 1: Scheme to illustrate the computation of the fluid trajectories for the case of quadratic elements. Assuming we know the forward-in-time trajectories of the mesh nodes (gray), we construct new isoparametric elements (green) and convect the inner points of the elements so that each $\mathbf{x} \in K$ and $\mathbf{X}_h(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \tilde{K}_h(t)$ (red trajectory) share the same natural coordinates $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ in the reference element \tilde{K} .

130 2.3. Boundary conditions

131 As usual in the literature, to allow for the imposition of Dirichlet conditions in the strong sense, we
 132 define the auxiliary spaces

$$V_{h,D} := \{v_h \in V_h : v_h|_{\Gamma_D} = L_h u_D|_{\Gamma_D}\},$$

$$V_{h,0} := \{v_h \in V_h : v_h|_{\Gamma_D} = 0\}.$$

¹The latter procedure is not sufficient for ensuring that the element is not distorted. However, it performs well in practice if we consider a sufficient number of points –e.g., the nodes corresponding to high-order quadrature rules.

133 Here, Γ_D is the Dirichlet boundary, L_h is the Lagrange interpolation operator onto \mathbb{T}_h , and u_D represents
 134 the prescribed value for u . Similarly, we define the spaces

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{V}_{h,D}(t) &:= \left\{ v_h \in \tilde{V}_h(t) : v_h|_{\tilde{\Gamma}_D(t)} = \tilde{L}_h u_D|_{\tilde{\Gamma}_D(t)} \right\}, \\ \tilde{V}_{h,0}(t) &:= \left\{ v_h \in \tilde{V}_h(t) : v_h|_{\tilde{\Gamma}_D(t)} = 0 \right\},\end{aligned}$$

135 associated with the convected mesh $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$, with $\tilde{\Gamma}_D(t)$ the Dirichlet boundary of $\tilde{\Omega}_h(t)$ and \tilde{L}_h the Lagrange
 136 interpolation operator onto $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$. It is a major assumption that the Dirichlet conditions are known both
 137 for the fixed mesh \mathbb{T}_h and for the convected mesh $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$.

138 2.4. Time discretization

139 In what follows, $(\cdot)^n$ refers to any variable evaluated at t^n and

$$(u, v)_D = \int_D uv \, d\Omega$$

140 denotes the scalar product of two variables over a generic domain D .

141 Let us assume that an approximation $u_h^n \in V_h$ to $u(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$ is given and that we want to obtain an
 142 approximation to $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ at time t^{n+1} . First, we choose a fluid volume Ω_f which coincides with Ω_h at t^n , i.e.,
 143 $\Omega_f(t^n) \equiv \Omega_h$. According to Section 2.2, we can make the approximation $\Omega_f(t) \simeq \Omega_h(t)$. Then, we consider
 144 the following semi-discrete version of (2): find $w_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,D}$ such that

$$\frac{d}{dt} (w_h, v_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} = 0, \quad \forall v_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,0}. \quad (5)$$

145 Eq. (5) provides a non-stabilized approximation $w_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ to $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ which suffers from spurious oscillations
 146 if the solution is discontinuous or presents sharp gradients². From w_h , we compute a subgrid stabilization
 147 operator, $S_{SS} = S_{SS}(w_h; u_h, v_h)$, and a discontinuity-capturing operator, $S_{DC} = S_{DC}(w_h; u_h, v_h)$, which allow
 148 to obtain a stabilized solution $u_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,D}$ through the equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} (u_h, v_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h} = -S_{SS}(w_h; u_h, v_h) - S_{DC}(w_h; u_h, v_h), \quad \forall v_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,0}. \quad (6)$$

149 Both operators are stiff and linear with respect to u_h , although they depend nonlinearly on the non-stabilized
 150 solution w_h , making the stabilization approach non-linear. We take $w_h^n = u_h^n$ and recall that $\tilde{\Omega}_h(t^n) = \Omega_h$ in
 151 Eqs. (5)-(6). To solve (5)-(6), we also must displace the mesh \mathbb{T}_h forward in time through the equation

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\chi}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{a}(u_h(\boldsymbol{\chi}_i, t), \boldsymbol{\chi}_i, t), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_h, \quad (7)$$

152 where the velocity field has been written in the form $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(u, \mathbf{x}, t)$ for the sake of generality.

153 An implicit-explicit Runge–Kutta method is employed to solve the fully coupled system formed by Eqs.
 154 (5)-(7). To describe the implicit (I) and explicit (E) parts of the method, we employ the Butcher tableaux

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc|cccc} c^1 = 0 & 0 & & & & 0 & & & & \\ c^2 & a_I^{2,1} & a_I^{2,2} & & & a_E^{2,1} & & & & \\ c^3 & a_I^{3,1} & a_I^{3,2} & a_I^{3,2} & & a_E^{3,1} & a_E^{3,2} & & & \\ \vdots & \vdots & & & \ddots & \vdots & & & \ddots & \\ c^s & a_I^{s,1} & \dots & \dots & a_I^{s,s} & a_E^{s,1} & \dots & \dots & a_E^{s,s-1} & \\ \hline & b_I^1 & \dots & \dots & b_I^s & b_E^1 & \dots & \dots & b_E^{s-1} & b_E^s \end{array}. \quad (8)$$

²Even though if the solution is smooth, w_h may turn unstable for small time steps as no kind of subgrid stabilization has been applied [32, 51].

155 Note that we consider methods with the same time splitting for both parts. When $b_I^j = a_I^{s,j}$ and $b_E^j = a_E^{s,j}$ for
 156 $j = 1, \dots, s$, the solution at t^{n+1} is the same than that of the last internal stage –and therefore it is computed
 157 implicitly– and the method is said to be *globally stiffly accurate*, according to the definition in [55]. We
 158 have found that methods with this property perform significantly better for the equations considered in this
 159 work.

160 To integrate Eqs. (5)–(7), we start by setting the following variables for the first stage of the Runge–
 161 Kutta:

$$t^{[1]} = t^n, \quad \boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[1]} = \mathbf{x}_i, \quad w_h^{[1]} = u_h^n, \quad u_h^{[1]} = u_h^n, \quad \tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]} = \Omega_h, \\ \mathbf{f}_i^{[1]} = \mathbf{a}\left(u_h^{[1]}(\boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[1]}, t^{[1]}), \boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[1]}, t^{[1]}\right), \quad g^{[1]}(v_h) = -S_{\text{SS}}(w_h^{[1]}; u_h^{[1]}, v_h^{[1]}) - S_{\text{DC}}(w_h^{[1]}; u_h^{[1]}, v_h^{[1]}). \quad (9)$$

162 Then, for the stages $j = 2, \dots, s$, we set $t^{[j]} = t^n + c^j \Delta t$, with $\Delta t = t^{n+1} - t^n$, and displace the mesh nodes
 163 forward-in-time with the explicit part of the method, i.e.,

$$\boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[j]} = \boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[1]} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} a_E^{jk} \mathbf{f}_i^{[k]}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_h. \quad (10)$$

164 According to Section 2.2, the convected nodes define the convected mesh $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[j]}$, the convected finite element
 165 space $\tilde{V}_h^{[j]} = P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[j]})$ and the convected domain $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[j]}$. Then, we compute the non-stabilized solution
 166 $w_h^{[j]} \in \tilde{V}_{h,D}^{[j]}$ given by

$$\left(w_h^{[j]}, v_h^{[j]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[j]}} = \left(w_h^{[1]}, v_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}}, \quad \forall v_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,0}. \quad (11)$$

167 The solution $w_h^{[j]}$ is post-processed to detect oscillations and compute adequate stabilization operators (see
 168 Sections 2.5–2.6). With these operators, we now compute the stabilized solution $u_h^{[j]} \in \tilde{V}_{h,D}^{[j]}$ given by

$$\left(u_h^{[j]}, v_h^{[j]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[j]}} + a_I^{jj} \Delta t S_{\text{SS}}(w_h^{[j]}; u_h^{[j]}, v_h^{[j]}) + a_I^{jj} \Delta t S_{\text{DC}}(w_h^{[j]}; u_h^{[j]}, v_h^{[j]}) = \\ \left(u_h^{[1]}, v_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} a_I^{jk} g^{[k]}(v_h), \quad \forall v_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,0}, \quad (12)$$

169 evaluate the terms

$$\mathbf{f}_i^{[j]} = \mathbf{a}\left(u_h^{[j]}(\boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[j]}, t^{[j]}), \boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[j]}, t^{[j]}\right), \quad (13)$$

$$g^{[j]}(v_h) = -S_{\text{SS}}(u_h^{[j]}; u_h^{[j]}, v_h^{[j]}) - S_{\text{DC}}(u_h^{[j]}; u_h^{[j]}, v_h^{[j]}), \quad (14)$$

170 and go to the next stage if $j < s$. Otherwise, we compute the solution at t^{n+1} through the equations

$$\boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{n+1} = \boldsymbol{\chi}_i^{[1]} + \Delta t \sum_{k=1}^s b_E^k \mathbf{f}_i^{[k]}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_h, \quad (15)$$

$$\left(u_h^{n+1}, v_h^{n+1}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}} = \left(u_h^{[1]}, v_h^{[1]}\right)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{[1]}} + \Delta t \sum_{j=1}^s b_I^j g^{[j]}(v_h), \quad \forall v_h \in \tilde{V}_{h,0}. \quad (16)$$

171 We strongly recall that, in the equations above, when $v_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the i -th shape function of $\tilde{V}_h(t)$, $v_h^{[j]}(\mathbf{x})$ is
 172 the i -th shape function of $\tilde{V}_h^{[j]}$ for any stage j , according to Section 2.2.

173 The last stage of the Runge–Kutta method corresponds to $t^{n+1} = t^{[s]}$ and provides a finite element
 174 solution $\tilde{u}_h^{n+1} \in \tilde{V}_{h,D}^{n+1}$ defined over the convected mesh $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$ (the tilde symbol in \tilde{u}_h^{n+1} is used to emphasize
 175 that the solution is defined on the convected mesh). This solution has to be transferred to the fixed mesh
 176 \mathbb{T}_h in order to proceed again as shown above and compute a solution at t^{n+2} . In semi-Lagrangian methods,
 177 this is achieved by means of an interpolation procedure; however, in Lagrange–Galerkin methods, we take

178 the L^2 projection onto the fixed mesh, which minimizes the L^2 error between u_h^{n+1} and \tilde{u}_h^{n+1} [23]. That is,
 179 we find $u_h^{n+1} \in V_{h,D}$ such that

$$(u_h^{n+1}, v_h^{n+1})_{\Omega_h} = (\tilde{u}_h^{n+1}, v_h^{n+1})_{\Omega_h}, \quad \forall v_h^{n+1} \in V_{h,0}. \quad (17)$$

180 It must be noted that u_h^{n+1} may suffer from spurious oscillations when the solution is discontinuous or
 181 presents sharp gradients. These oscillations are not a problem because they are killed by artificial diffusion
 182 when integrating from t^{n+1} to t^{n+2} . However, note that it is more accurate to take \tilde{u}_h^{n+1} as the solution at
 183 t^{n+1} and to consider (17) as the first step for integrating from t^{n+1} to t^{n+2} , rather than to consider (17) as
 184 the last step for integrating from t^n to t^{n+1} and to take u_h^{n+1} as the solution at t^{n+1} .

185 The following remarks are in order:

- 186 (i) The right-hand side in (17) represents the scalar product of two functions $-\tilde{u}_h^{n+1}$ and v_h^{n+1} — that are
 187 defined piecewise on different meshes $-\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$ and \mathbb{T}_h , respectively—, as seen in Fig. 2. Thus, a possible
 188 approach to compute this term would be to employ mesh intersection techniques [56–58]. However,
 189 these techniques are complicated to implement and, as far as we know, they have not been developed
 190 yet for curvilinear meshes, as is the case of this work. Hence, here we follow [59] and integrate with
 191 respect to the elements in \mathbb{T}_h with high-order quadrature rules—see [32] for implementation details.
 192 Note that this procedure requires to employ a search-locate algorithm [60, 61] to evaluate \tilde{u}_h^{n+1} at the
 193 quadrature nodes of \mathbb{T}_h .
- 194 (ii) When there is flow entering the domain through part of the boundary—i.e., $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} < 0$ —, part of the domain
 195 Ω_h remains outside of the convected domain $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}$ (see also Fig. 2). In those cases, the solution \tilde{u}_h^{n+1}
 196 (defined on $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}$) is assumed to be equal to some known (incoming) flow conditions $u_{\text{in}}(\mathbf{x}, t^{n+1})$ in
 197 the region $\Omega_h \setminus \tilde{\Omega}_h^{n+1}$ so as to compute the right-hand side of (17). Note that this procedure is a way of
 198 weakly imposing Dirichlet conditions at the inflow boundary.

Figure 2: Scheme that illustrates the domains and meshes that appear in the formulation. The elements in \mathbb{T}_h are convected forward in time with the flow velocity field to form $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$. The variables u_h^{n+1} and v_h^{n+1} in Eq. (17) are defined piecewise in \mathbb{T}_h , whereas \tilde{u}_h^{n+1} is defined piecewise in $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$.

199 Next we address the computation of the discontinuity-capturing and subgrid stabilization operators.

200 2.5. Discontinuity-capturing operator

201 The discontinuity-capturing (DC) operator developed here is based on post-processing the non-stabilized
 202 solution w_h as follows. First, we employ the values of the fine-scale term w'_h to locate the discontinuities.

203 More specifically, we define the fluctuation operator $\tilde{\kappa}_h = \mathbb{I} - \tilde{L}_h$, with \mathbb{I} the identity operator (recall that \tilde{L}_h
204 denotes the Lagrange interpolation operator onto $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$), and compute the error

$$e_K := \frac{\left[\int_K (\tilde{\kappa}_h w_h)^2 \, d\Omega / \int_K d\Omega \right]^{1/2}}{\left[\int_{\Omega_h} (\bar{w}_h)^2 \, d\Omega / \int_{\Omega_h} d\Omega \right]^{1/2}},$$

205 for each element $K \in \tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$. Note from Eq. (3) that $\tilde{\kappa}_h w_h = \tilde{\kappa}_h w_h'$. Hence, e_K is proportional to the root
206 mean square of $\tilde{\kappa}_h w_h'$ over K . Since the fine-scale term can be seen in (3) as a measure of the error in the
207 large-scale term [62], e_K is thus expected to be large at the vicinities of the discontinuity and small at the
208 zones where the solution is smooth. Also note that e_K is dimensionless.

209 Second, if we modify Eq. (2) by adding a diffusion term of the form $(\epsilon \nabla u, \nabla v)_{\Omega_f}$ to the left-hand side,
210 with $\epsilon = \epsilon(\mathbf{x}, t)$ a given diffusion coefficient, then each discontinuity is transformed into a transition layer.
211 If the thickness of a transition layer, δ , is of the order of h/r , with h the mesh size, then the layer is wide
212 enough to be captured with the finite element discretization, and also narrow enough to represent the original
213 discontinuity without excessive smearing. Thus, we seek to apply an artificial diffusion ϵ at the vicinities of
214 the discontinuities so that the thicknesses of the corresponding transition layers result of the order of h/r .
215 In particular, due to physical principles, we impose

$$\epsilon \sim \hat{a} \frac{h}{r}, \quad (18)$$

216 with

$$\hat{a} := \left| \frac{\partial(\mathbf{a}u)}{\partial u} \right| \quad (19)$$

217 a simplifying approximation to the velocity of the discontinuity. The analytical expression of \hat{a} in terms
218 of \mathbf{x} , t and/or u is assumed to be available. Note that the solution at the transition layer is continuous
219 and therefore it makes sense to take derivatives in (19). From (18), we define at each element $K \in \tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h(t)$ a
220 diffusion coefficient

$$\epsilon_K := \hat{a}_K \frac{h_K}{r} S_K, \quad (20)$$

221 with

$$\hat{a}_K := \left[\int_K \hat{a}^2(\bar{w}_h) \, d\Omega / \int_K d\Omega \right]^{1/2}, \quad (21)$$

222 $h_K = \left[\int_K d\Omega \right]^{1/2}$ and

$$S_K := \min \{ C_\epsilon^t e_K, C_{\max} \} \quad (22)$$

223 the so-called discontinuity sensor. In (22), C_ϵ^t is a positive user-defined constant employed to fine-tune
224 the quantity of diffusion that is added, whereas $C_{\max} \sim 1$ is another positive user-defined constant that
225 guarantees that the applied diffusion is never excessive –recall that a diffusion $\epsilon_K \sim \hat{a}_K h_K / r$ is theoretically
226 enough to capture any discontinuity, irrespective of its magnitude.

227 The ϵ_K 's define an element-wise continuous diffusion. However, smoother results can be obtained if
228 the applied diffusion is continuous at the whole domain [43, 46]. For that purpose, we perform a linear
229 reconstruction [63] to obtain a continuous, piece-wise linear diffusion coefficient $\epsilon_h(w_h; \mathbf{x}, t)$. Briefly speaking,
230 ϵ_h is defined at each vertex of the mesh as a weighted average of the ϵ_K 's of the corresponding elements. In
231 this work, we took the inverses of the areas of the corresponding elements as the weights of the formula.

232 Once $\epsilon_h(w_h; \mathbf{x}, t)$ has been computed, we define the discontinuity-capturing term in Eq. (6) as

$$S_{\text{DC}}(w_h; u_h, v_h) = (\epsilon_h \nabla u_h, \nabla v_h)_{\tilde{\Omega}_h}.$$

2.6. Subgrid stabilization

The DC operator introduced before is able to detect and stabilize the severe oscillations that appear at the vicinities of the discontinuities. However, it is not able to detect the (initially) small instabilities that appear in the smooth regions as a consequence of the inexact computation of the integrals in the formulation. Therefore, it is necessary to add another stabilization term to kill these instabilities. In our case, we have adopted the subgrid stabilization (SS) method [52, 64], which consists on adding some diffusion in the fine-scale terms of the solution. Although there are many other possibilities to perform the SS –see, e.g., [52]–, here we consider the term

$$S_{SS}(w_h; u_h, v_h) = \sum_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} C_{SS} \widehat{a}_K \frac{h_K}{r} (\nabla \widetilde{\kappa}_h u_h, \nabla \widetilde{\kappa}_h v_h)_K$$

in Eq. (6), with $C_{SS} \geq 0$ a dimensionless user-defined constant. We have seen in several numerical experiments that the value of C_{SS} does not affect sensitively the results once stability is achieved. Thus, we set a constant value $C_{SS} = 100$ –which is large enough to ensure stability– for the rest of the paper.

It must be pointed that the SS employed here is very related to the local projection stabilization (LPS) used in some of our previous works –e.g. [22, 32, 51]. The LPS considers fluctuations of gradients instead of gradients of fluctuations and defines the fluctuation operator in a slightly different way. Here, we adopt the SS because it is easier to implement in curvilinear meshes and is spectrally equivalent to the LPS (see Lemma IV.4.25 in [52]).

2.7. Summary of the scheme and remarks

The scheme described in previous sections is summarized in Algorithm 1 and will be referred hereafter as the Runge–Kutta forward Lagrange–Galerkin (RK-FLG) scheme.

Algorithm 1: Step from t^n to t^{n+1} of the RK-FLG method.

Data: convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^n$ and solution $\widetilde{u}_h^n(\mathbf{x}) \in \widetilde{V}_h^n$ at t^n ; reference mesh \mathbb{T}_h and space V_h ; velocity field $\mathbf{a}(u, \mathbf{x}, t)$; inflow conditions $u_{in}(\mathbf{x}, t)$; time step Δt , Butcher tableaux (8).

- 1 **perform** the L^2 projection of \widetilde{u}_h^n onto the fixed finite element space V_h (Eq. (17) with $n+1$ replaced by n) to obtain $u_h^n \in V_h$,
 - 2 **set** $t^{[1]} = t^n$, $w_h^{[1]} = u_h^n$, $u_h^{[1]} = u_h^n$, $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[1]} = \mathbb{T}_h$ and other variables in Eq. (9),
 - 3 **for** $j = 2, \dots, s$ **do**
 - 4 **compute** convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[j]}$ from Eq. (10),
 - 5 **compute** non-stabilized solution $w_h^{[j]}$ by solving (11),
 - 6 **compute** ϵ_K with Eq. (20) for all $K \in \widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{[j]}$,
 - 7 **compute** ϵ_h via a linear reconstruction of the ϵ_K 's,
 - 8 **compute** discontinuity-capturing and subgrid stabilization operators,
 - 9 **compute** stabilized solution $u_h^{[j]}$ by solving (12),
 - 10 **compute** derivatives $\mathbf{f}_i^{[j]}$ and $g^{[j]}(v_h)$ from Eqs. (13)-(14),
 - 11 **end**
 - 12 **compute** convected mesh $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$ and solution \widetilde{u}_h^{n+1} from Eqs. (15)-(16).
- Result:** $\widetilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n+1}$, $\widetilde{u}_h^{n+1} \in \widetilde{V}_h^{n+1}$.
-

The initial value $u_h^0 \in V_{h,D}$ is taken in some Lagrange–Galerkin methods as the L^2 projection of a given smooth initial condition $u^0(\mathbf{x})$ onto the space V_h , i.e.,

$$(u_h^0, v_h)_{\Omega_h} = (u^0, v_h)_{\Omega_h}, \quad \forall v_h \in V_{h,0}. \quad (23)$$

The latter formula leads to spurious oscillations when applied to discontinuous initial conditions. Although these oscillations are to be killed via artificial diffusion, it may be helpful to start with a smoother initial condition. For that purpose, we employ a DC operator similar to that shown in Section 2.5, with the only

258 difference that now the relation between the diffusion coefficient and the transition layer is given by $\epsilon \sim \delta^2$.
 259 That is, we take w_h^0 as the result of (23), replace formula (20) by

$$\epsilon_K := \left(\frac{h_K}{r} \right)^2 \min \{ C_\epsilon^0 e_K, C_{\max} \},$$

260 with C_ϵ^0 a positive user-defined parameter –not to be confused with C_ϵ^t in (20)–, and find $u_h^0 \in V_{h,D}$ such
 261 that

$$(u_h^0, v_h)_{\Omega_h} + (\epsilon_h \nabla u_h^0, \nabla v_h)_{\Omega_h} = (u^0, v_h)_{\Omega_h}, \quad \forall v_h \in V_h. \quad (24)$$

262 On the other hand, the time step Δt may be fixed along the simulation or may vary to respect a fixed
 263 CFL condition. In the latter case, we set

$$t^{n+1} - t^n = \text{CFL} \min_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} \left\{ \frac{h_K/r}{\widehat{a}_K} \right\},$$

264 where \widehat{a}_K is computed through Eq. (21) considering $t = t^n$ and $w_h = u_h^n$.

265 It is worth remarking that the RK-FLG above can be simplified when no discontinuity-capturing is to
 266 be applied. In effect, in the latter case we can consider a subgrid stabilization operator of the form

$$S_{\text{SS}}^*(u_h, v_h) = \sum_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} C_{\text{SS}} \widehat{a}_0 \frac{h_K}{r} (\nabla \widetilde{\kappa}_h u_h, \nabla \widetilde{\kappa}_h v_h)_K,$$

267 with \widehat{a}_0 a characteristic velocity –e.g., $\widehat{a}_0 = 1.0$, ignoring physical units–, and directly solve

$$\frac{d}{dt} (u_h, v_h)_{\widetilde{\Omega}_h} = -S_{\text{SS}}^*(u_h, v_h), \quad \forall v_h \in \widetilde{V}_{h,0},$$

268 instead of (5)-(6), which is the common procedure in stabilized Lagrange–Galerkin methods –e.g. [22, 32, 51].

269 Finally, it must be pointed that the RK-FLG scheme is (nearly) mass-conservative when there is no fluid
 270 entering nor leaving the domain –i.e. $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ at the whole boundary– and there are no strongly applied
 271 Dirichlet conditions. In effect, in these cases, $\Omega_f(t) \equiv \Omega_h$ for all t , whereas the test function $v_h \equiv 1$ belongs
 272 to the test space $\widetilde{V}_{h,0}$. Furthermore, it can easily be checked that $S_{\text{SS}}(w_h; u_h, 1) = S_{\text{DC}}(w_h; u_h, 1) = 0$ for all
 273 u_h and w_h . Hence, Eq. (16) provides

$$(\widetilde{u}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (u_h^{[1]}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (u_h^n, 1)_{\Omega_h},$$

274 whereas Eq. (17) yields

$$(u_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (\widetilde{u}_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h}.$$

275 Therefore, taking into account Eq. (24),

$$(u_h^{n+1}, 1)_{\Omega_h} = (u_h^n, 1)_{\Omega_h} = \dots = (u^0, 1)_{\Omega_h}, \quad (25)$$

276 which states that mass is preserved. Note that the integrals in the formulation must be computed exactly in
 277 order to achieve exact mass conservation. However, as explained before, the right-hand side of Eq. (17) can
 278 only be computed exactly via mesh intersection techniques. If high-order quadrature rules are used instead,
 279 as in this work, Eq. (25) is satisfied only with high accuracy. Hence, we shall say that the RK-FLG method
 280 is *nearly* conservative.

281 2.8. On the advantages of the forward method with respect to the classic backward formulation

282 In most part of Lagrange–Galerkin and semi-Lagrangian methods, the fluid trajectories are computed
 283 backward in time. That is, \mathbb{T}_h is displaced from t^{n+1} to t^n instead of from t^n to t^{n+1} . As an advantage, the

284 solution at t^{n+1} provided by the Lagrangian formulation is defined directly on the reference space V_h , and
 285 not on the convected space \tilde{V}_h^{n+1} as in our case.

286 However, it is somehow difficult to compute the trajectories from t^{n+1} to t^n when the solution at t^{n+1} is
 287 not known yet. In effect, to do so, one may extrapolate in time the velocity fields from previous solutions
 288 [29, 40] and compute the fluid trajectories, e.g., with a Runge–Kutta method or the implicit midpoint
 289 rule. Irrespective of the time-integration rule employed, this approach is explicit in the sense that those
 290 trajectories do not depend on u_h^{n+1} . We have tried this approach and experienced many stability issues
 291 due to this fact. Another procedure consists on forcing the trajectories to depend on u_h^{n+1} and to solve for
 292 u_h^{n+1} with implicit or predictor-corrector methods [65, 66]. This approach is more stable but also expensive.
 293 Additionally, none of the approaches above is self-starting for time-discretizations higher than second order.

294 In contrast, forward methods yield a more clear time-discretization of arbitrary order, and are self-starting
 295 if Runge–Kutta rules are employed as in our case. Also note that it is more straightforward to analyze their
 296 stability, as the latter is directly governed by the stability region of the considered time-marching formula.

297 3. Numerical experiments

298 In this section, we first test the RK-FLG method and the stabilized L^2 projection (24) on several two-
 299 dimensional benchmark problems to check their accuracy. In particular, we focus on the convergence rate
 300 of the normalized L^1 error, e_{L^1} , and of the normalized error of mass, e_m , at the final time T , i.e.,

$$e_{L^1} = \frac{\int_{\Omega_h} |u_h(\mathbf{x}, T) - u(\mathbf{x}, T)| \, d\Omega(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{\Omega_h} |u(\mathbf{x}, T)| \, d\Omega(\mathbf{x})}, \quad e_m = \left| \frac{\int_{\Omega_h} [u_h(\mathbf{x}, T) - u(\mathbf{x}, T)] \, d\Omega(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{\Omega_h} u(\mathbf{x}, T) \, d\Omega(\mathbf{x})} \right|,$$

301 with respect to the mesh size h and to the time step Δt (for the cases of prescribed velocity field $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$)
 302 or the CFL number (for the cases $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(u)$)³. Here, the mesh size is defined as $h = \sqrt{(4|\Omega_h|/\sqrt{3}N_E)}$, with
 303 $|\Omega_h| = \int_{\Omega_h} d\Omega$ and N_E the number of elements (i.e., if all the elements were equilateral triangles of the same
 304 size, h would represent the side sizes of those triangles). Afterwards, we perform some additional simulations
 305 to study the computational efficiency of the RK-FLG method.

306 It should be pointed that here we do not show the behavior of the well-known L^2 error in order to save
 307 space. However, we have seen in the numerical experiments that it behaves very similar to the L^1 error
 308 when the solution is smooth, whereas for discontinuous solutions it behaves as $\mathcal{O}(h^{1/2})$, as expected.

309 The tests are distributed as follows:

- 310 ■ Tests I-a and I-b deal with the stabilized L^2 projection (24) of different initial conditions.
- 311 ■ Test II addresses the case of prescribed velocity field $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$.
- 312 ■ Tests III-a and III-b consider the Burgers equation –that is, $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(u) = (u/2, u/2)$ –, to check the ability
 313 of the method to capture shock waves that are generated at arbitrary time instants from smooth initial
 314 conditions.
- 315 ■ Test IV is the Kurganov-Petrova-Popov example [67] defined by $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(u) = (\sin u/u, (\cos u - 1)/u)$,
 316 which leads to composite waves and thus it is usually considered hard to solve [68].

317 In all cases, we employ straight triangular meshes generated with GMSH software [69] and space discre-
 318 tizations up to fourth-order. To integrate in time, we consider the third-order Runge–Kutta method (4,4,3)

³As it is well known, in the case $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}(u)$ it is more preferable to study the convergence rates with respect to h for a fixed CFL number than for a fixed Δt due to stability reasons.

319 developed by Ascher et al. [70], which is given by the tableaux

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc|cccc}
 0 & 0 & & & & 0 & & & & \\
 \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & & & \frac{1}{2} & & & & \\
 \frac{2}{3} & 0 & \frac{1}{6} & \frac{1}{2} & & \frac{11}{18} & \frac{1}{18} & & & \\
 \frac{1}{2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{5}{6} & -\frac{5}{5} & \frac{1}{2} & & \\
 1 & 0 & \frac{3}{2} & -\frac{3}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{7}{4} & \frac{3}{4} & -\frac{7}{4} \\
 \hline
 & 0 & \frac{3}{2} & -\frac{3}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4} & \frac{7}{4} & \frac{3}{4} & -\frac{7}{4} & 0
 \end{array} ,$$

320 has an L -stable implicit part and is globally stiffly accurate. We have also tried some other higher-order
 321 schemes –e.g. [71]– but have not obtained good results as those are not globally stiffly accurate. The
 322 integrals in the formulation are evaluated via 175-node quadrature rules [72], which are exact for 30th-
 323 degree polynomials. The codes were implemented in Julia language [73].

324 3.1. Stabilized L^2 projection of the initial condition

325 3.1.1. Test I-a: Projection of a discontinuous function

326 Here, we consider the stabilized projection (24) of the discontinuous function $u^0(\mathbf{x}) = \sin(\pi(x_1 + x_2)/2) +$
 327 $2\sigma(x_2 - x_1)$, with $\sigma(t)$ the Heaviside function, in the domain $[-1, 1]^2$. We set $C_{\max} = 2.0$. As can be seen
 328 in Figs. 3 and 4, the oscillations at the discontinuity are suppressed when the DC operator is applied. Note
 329 that the solution does not seem to be very sensitive to C_ϵ^0 once stability is achieved. Also observe in Fig. 4
 330 that the stabilized solutions are not very dependent on the order of the space discretization whenever the
 331 average distance between nodes, h/r , is similar.

Figure 3: Solution of Test I-a for P_2^{bubble} elements and $h/r = 0.00892$. Left image corresponds to $C_\epsilon^0 = 0.0$ –i.e., the non-stabilized solution–; right image corresponds to $C_\epsilon^0 = 5.0$.

Figure 4: View of the solution of Test I-a at the segment line $-0.04 \leq x_1 \leq 0.04$, $x_2 = 0$ for different values of r and C_ϵ^0 . Note that $h/r \simeq 0.009$ in all cases. Cross markers represent the edges of the elements.

332 In addition, Fig. 5 shows that the L^1 error behaves as $\mathcal{O}(h/r)$ for a fixed value of C_ϵ^0 , which is the
 333 optimal convergence rate for polynomial approximations of any order r [43]. The latter is due to the fact
 334 that, in this case, the L^1 error is dominated by the error at discontinuity, which is captured with a resolution
 335 scale h/r . Also note that the L^1 error increases with C_ϵ^0 , since the latter tends to smear the discontinuity.
 336 Finally, it is seen that the errors of mass are close to machine precision.

Figure 5: L^1 and mass errors of Test I-a as functions of h/r for different values of C_ϵ^0 and for $r = 1$ (\circ), $r = 2$ (\triangle), $r = 3$ (\square) and $r = 4$ (\star).

3.1.2. Test I-b: Projection of a smooth function

In this test, we consider the stabilized L^2 projection (24) of the continuous function $u^0(\mathbf{x}) = 1 + \sin(\pi(x_1 + x_2)/2)$ in the domain $[-1, 1]^2$, for the purpose of checking if the proposed DC operator does not spoil the convergence rate of the standard L^2 projection (23). We set $C_{\max} = 2.0$ again.

In effect, Fig. 6 shows that the optimal convergence rate $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$ for the L^1 error is kept. Moreover, it is seen that the solution becomes almost identical to that of the standard projection when h decreases. Note that we have employed the same values for C_ϵ^0 than in Test I-a. Thus, it is seen that the proposed DC operator is able to capture discontinuities with enough accuracy at the same time that it leaves the solution unaffected when the latter is smooth. This property stems from the fact that the quantity of artificial diffusion added by the DC operator is based on the values of the bubble degrees of freedom of the so-called non-stabilized solution, which are very small at regions where the solution is smooth. Therefore, almost no diffusion is applied the latter regions. Also observe in Fig. 6 that the errors of mass are very close to machine precision.

Figure 6: L^1 and mass errors of Test I-b as functions of h/r for different values of C_ϵ^0 and for $r = 1$ (\circ), $r = 2$ (\triangle), $r = 3$ (\square) and $r = 4$ (\star).

350 3.2. Prescribed velocity field

351 3.2.1. Test II: Rigid-body rotation of a slotted cylinder and a hump

352 In this test, we consider a slotted cylinder and a hump that are located on different places of the domain
 353 $[-1, 1]^2$ and are simultaneously rotated around the origin. In particular, the cylinder is of height 1 and
 354 radius 0.25, is centered at $(0.5, 0)$ and has a slot along the plane $x_2 = 0$ of width 0.1 and depth 0.35, that is,

$$u_{\text{cyl}}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 1, & (x_1 - 0.5)^2 + x_2^2 \leq 1 \text{ and } (x_1 < 0.4 \text{ or } |x_2| > 0.05) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

355 whereas the hump is given by

$$u_{\text{hump}}(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} \cos^3(1.5\pi r_{\text{hump}}), & r_{\text{hump}} \leq 1/3, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

356 with $r_{\text{hump}}^2 = (x_1 + 0.5)^2 + x_2^2$. Both the cylinder and the hump are subject to the velocity field $\mathbf{a} = 2\pi(-x_2, x_1)$
 357 during a total time $T = 1$. No Dirichlet conditions are strongly applied at the boundary. In all the simulations,
 358 we have considered a fixed value $C_\epsilon^0 = 1.0$ for projecting the initial condition and $C_{\text{max}} = 2.0$.

359 Figs. 7 and 8 show the ability of the method to capture the discontinuities at the slotted cylinder without
 360 excessive smearing. Note that, again, the results are not very depend on r whenever h/r remains similar,
 361 although the solutions are slightly less diffusive for higher r . In addition, it is seen in Fig. 9 that the
 362 hump is not smeared, which demonstrates that the DC operator adds diffusion only at the vicinities of the
 363 discontinuity, as desired.

Figure 7: Slotted cylinder after one revolution for P_2^{bubble} elements, $h/r = 0.00892$ and $\Delta t = 0.01$. Left image corresponds to $C_\epsilon^t = 0.0$ –i.e., the non-stabilized solution–; right image corresponds to $C_\epsilon^t = 0.5$.

Figure 8: View of the slotted cylinder at the segment line $x_1 = 0.5$, $-0.35 \leq x_2 \leq 0.35$ for $\Delta t = 0.01$ and for different values of r and C_ϵ^t . Note that $h/r \approx 0.009$ in all cases.

Figure 9: View of the solution of Test II at the segment line $-1 \leq x_1 \leq 1$, $x_2 = 0$ for $\Delta t = 0.01$ and for different values of r and C_ϵ^t . Note that $h/r \simeq 0.009$ in all cases.

364 In addition, we have measured separately the L^1 and the mass errors at the zones of the hump ($x_1 < 0$)
 365 and of the cylinder ($x_1 \geq 0$). As can be seen in Fig. 10, the L^1 error behaves clearly as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^3)$ for the
 366 case of the hump, as expected. For the case of the cylinder, the L^1 error also behaves as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^3)$ for Δt
 367 above a certain value. Below that value, the error of the space discretization—which is more noticeable than
 368 in the case of the hump because of the discontinuity—becomes dominant and thus the L^1 error remains
 369 constant with Δt , or even increases slightly with Δt [74]. On the other hand, the errors of mass show an
 370 erratic behavior with respect to C_ϵ^t and Δt , as expected since the formulation is theoretically conservative

371 irrespective of these parameters.

Figure 10: L^1 and mass errors of Test II as functions of Δt for $h/r \simeq 0.009$, for different values of C_ϵ^t and for $r = 1$ (\circ), $r = 2$ (Δ), $r = 3$ (\square) and $r = 4$ (\star). Top images correspond to the case of the hump; bottom images corresponds to the case of the cylinder.

372 On the other hand, Fig. 11 shows that, for the case of the hump and quadratic elements, the L^1 error
 373 behaves as $\mathcal{O}(h^3)$ –or even better–, except for very small values of h , in which the error due to the time
 374 discretization becomes dominant and therefore the optimum convergence rate is lost. For the case of the
 375 cylinder, the L^1 error increases slightly slower than $\mathcal{O}(h)$ –except for the non-stabilized case $C_\epsilon^t = 0$ –, which
 376 means that the solution is more sensitive to the diffusion parameter C_ϵ^t for small h . In addition, it is seen
 377 that the error of mass is not very dependent on C_ϵ^t and increases with h . The latter is due to the fact
 378 that, when h is smaller, the right-hand side in (17) is computed with greater accuracy. The results are very
 379 similar for other values of r , although they are not shown to make the figures more legible.

Figure 11: L^1 and mass errors of Test II as functions of h for $\Delta t = 0.01$, for $r = 2$ and for different values of C_ϵ^t . Top images correspond to the case of the hump; bottom images correspond to the case of the cylinder.

3.3. Two-dimensional Burgers equation

3.3.1. Test III-a: Expansion wave and shock

For this test, we first consider the auxiliary 1D problem $\partial \tilde{u} / \partial t + \partial(\tilde{u}^2/2) / \partial \tilde{x} = 0$ subject to the initial condition

$$\tilde{u}(\tilde{x}, 0) = \begin{cases} 0.1\sqrt{2}, & \tilde{x} < -0.75 \\ 0.1\sqrt{2} + 0.9\sqrt{2} \frac{\tilde{x} + 0.75}{0.25}, & -0.75 \leq \tilde{x} < -0.50 \\ 1.0\sqrt{2}, & -0.50 \leq \tilde{x} < 0.25 \\ 1.0\sqrt{2} - 0.9\sqrt{2} \frac{\tilde{x} - 0.25}{0.25}, & 0.25 \leq \tilde{x} < 0.50 \\ 0.1\sqrt{2}, & \tilde{x} \geq 0.50, \end{cases}$$

whose analytical solution is straightforward to compute [75]. Then, we perform the change of variables $x_1 = \tilde{x} \cos(\pi/4)$, $x_2 = \tilde{x} \sin(\pi/4)$, $\tilde{u} = \sqrt{2}u$ to obtain an equation of the form (1) with $\mathbf{a} = (u/2, u/2)$, i.e., the well-known two-dimensional Burgers equation. The latter has been numerically solved considering the domain $[-1, 1]^2$, a diffusion parameter $C_\epsilon^0 = 1000$ for projecting the initial condition, $C_{\max} = 5.0$, a final time $T = 0.5$ and strong Dirichlet conditions at the inflow boundary.

389 The evolution of the solution from $t = 0$ to $t = T$ is shown in Fig. 12. As can be seen, there are two
 390 ramps at $t = 0$. The left ramp is expanded along the simulation, whereas the right one is transformed into a
 391 shock at $0.15 < t < 0.35$ –according to the analytical solution, the shock takes place at $t \approx 0.196$. Note that
 392 the method is able to capture and follow the shock front.

Figure 12: Numerical solution of Test III-a at different time instants for $CFL = 0.5$, $r = 4$, $h/r = 0.01625$ and $C_\epsilon^t = 1000$. The horizontal and vertical axis correspond to the x_1 and x_2 coordinates, respectively.

393 Furthermore, Figs. 13-14 show the values of the final solution at different segment lines for meshes with
 394 similar h/r . As can be seen, second, third and fourth-order elements provide similar solutions and are able
 395 to capture the discontinuity without spurious oscillations nor excessive diffusion at the ramp. This is not
 396 achieved for linear elements. Note that in this case the solution for $C_\epsilon^t = 0$ is not shown as it is extremely
 397 unstable. Also note that the diffusion parameter is much higher than for the case of prescribed velocity
 398 field. The latter is due to the fact that, now, the errors in the solution u_h lead to errors in the computation
 399 of the trajectories of the fluid particles which, at the same time, provoke errors in the computation of u_h .
 400 Thus, the scheme is less robust and needs more diffusion to suppress spurious oscillations.

Figure 13: View of the solution of Test III-a at the segment line $-1.5 \leq \tilde{x} \leq 1.5$ for $h/r \simeq 0.017$, for $CFL = 0.5$ and for different values of r and CFL .

Figure 14: View of the solution of Test III-a at the segment line $0.65 \leq \tilde{x} \leq 0.85$ for $h/r \approx 0.017$, for $CFL = 0.5$ and for different values of r and C_ϵ^t . Cross markers represent the edges of the elements.

401 On the other hand, Fig. 15 illustrates the effect of r on the solution when h , C_ϵ^t and the rest of parameters
402 are fixed –that is, the effect of the so-called p -refinement. It can be observed that, when r increases, the
403 solution is still smooth, and the discontinuity layer becomes r times thinner than that of the case of linear
404 elements, as expected. Hence, it is not necessary to modify C_ϵ^t to obtain accurate results in the case of
405 performing p -refinement.

Figure 15: Solution of Test III-a for $h = 0.065$, $CFL = 0.5$ and $C_\epsilon^t = 1000$ at the segment lines $-1.5 \leq \tilde{x} \leq 1.5$ (left) and $0.55 \leq \tilde{x} \leq 0.95$ (right). Cross markers represent the edges of the elements.

406 Finally, Fig. 16 shows the L^1 errors as a function of the CFL number and h/r . As can be seen, the errors
 407 increase very slightly with the CFL number and generally decrease with the order of the space discretization.
 408 Note that the method is able to achieve $CFL = 5.0$ except for the case $r = 4$ and $C_\epsilon^t = 100$, in which the
 409 solution turns unstable for $CFL \gtrsim 2.0$. It is also seen that the errors converge approximately as $\mathcal{O}((h/r)^{1.5})$.
 410 For brevity, here we do not show the errors of mass, which are not of interest now since there is fluid entering
 411 and leaving the domain and thus mass is not preserved.

Figure 16: Left: L^1 error of Test III-a as a function of the CFL number for $h/r \approx 0.017$. Right: L^1 error of Test III-a as a function of h/r for $CFL = 0.5$. Legend: (○) $r = 1$, (△) $r = 2$, (□) $r = 3$, (☆) $r = 4$.

412 3.3.2. Test III-b: Smooth solution

413 Here, we analyze the convergence properties of the RK-FLG method for the case in which the solution
 414 is always smooth. For that purpose, we proceed as with Test III-a, that is, we consider first the 1D Burgers

415 equation and then we transform it into the 2D Burgers equation by making a change of variables. In this
 416 case, $\tilde{u}(\tilde{x}, 0) = 1.5\sqrt{2} + \sqrt{2} \tanh(\tilde{x}/0.3)$, the domain is the square $[-1, 1]^2$, $T = 0.5$ and Dirichlet conditions
 417 are strongly applied at the inflow boundary. The analytical solution can be obtained as shown in [75]. The
 418 numerical solution of the 2D problem is computed considering a diffusion parameter $C_\epsilon^0 = 0$ for the initial
 419 condition and the same values for C_{\max}^t and C_ϵ^t than in Test III-a. The evolution of the solution from $t = 0$
 420 to $t = T$ is shown in Fig. 17.

Figure 17: Numerical solution of Test III-b at different time instants for $CFL = 0.5$, $r = 4$, $h/r = 0.01625$ and $C_\epsilon^t = 0$. The horizontal and vertical axis correspond to the x_1 and x_2 coordinates, respectively.

421 As can be seen in Fig. 18, the error slightly decreases with the CFL number when there is no diffusion.
 422 For $C_\epsilon^t > 0$, there seems to be a critical value of the CFL above which the error presents a sudden increase.
 423 Below that critical value, the results are almost identical to the non-stabilized case. It is also seen that the
 424 method is able to reach $CFL = 5.0$, except for the case $C_\epsilon = 0$. On the other hand, when $C_\epsilon^t = 0$ or the CFL is
 425 below the critical value, the errors behave as $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$ and are clearly smaller for higher-order discretizations.
 426 Otherwise, they behave as $\mathcal{O}((h/r)^3)$ and are not very dependent on the space discretization.

Figure 18: Left: L^1 error of Test III-b as a function of the CFL number for $h/r \approx 0.017$. Right: L^1 error of Test III-b as a function of h/r for $CFL = 0.5$. Legend: (○) $r = 1$, (△) $r = 2$, (□) $r = 3$, (☆) $r = 4$, (⋯) asymptote h^{r+1} .

427 As in Test III-b, mass is not preserved in the domain. Therefore, the errors of mass are not of interest
 428 and are not shown for brevity.

429 3.4. Kurganov-Petrova-Popov test

430 3.4.1. Test IV: Kurganov-Petrova-Popov test

431 Here, we reproduce the test by Kurganov, Petrova and Popov (KPP), which is given by $\mathbf{a} = (\sin u/u, (\cos u -$
 432 $1)/u)$,

$$u^0(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 3.5\pi, & x_1^2 + x_2^2 < 1, \\ 0.25\pi, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

433 and $T = 1$. The KPP test is usually considered hard to solve [68] due to the presence of a sonic point –placed
 434 at $(\cos(5\pi/8), \sin(5\pi/8))$ – and composite waves –i.e., expansion waves attached to shocks. To approach its
 435 numerical resolution, we have considered the domain $[-2, 2] \times [-2.5, 1.5]$, $C_\epsilon^0 = 1000$ and $C_{\max} = 5.0$. No
 436 analytical solution is known for this problem.

437 Fig. 19 shows the solution at the final time obtained with our method for CFL = 1.75 and fourth-order
 438 elements. As can be seen, the agreement with that of Kurganov et al [67] is very good. Also note that our
 439 method does not suffer from the sonic glitch problem –see examples in [67].

Figure 19: Numerical solution of the KPP test. Left: present method with $r = 4$, $h/r = 0.00945$, CFL = 1.75 and $C_\epsilon^t = 3500$. Right: MM1 method [67] for CFL = 0.5 and a cartesian grid with $\Delta x_1 = \Delta x_2 = 0.01$.

440 On the other hand, Fig. 20 shows the numerical solution at the segment line defined by $x_1(s) = -1 +$
 441 $2s/\sqrt{13}$, $x_2(s) = 1 - 3s/\sqrt{13}$, $0 \leq s \leq \sqrt{13}$, –i.e., from $(-1, 1)$ to $(1, -2)$ – for $r = 4$ and for different values of the
 442 CFL number and of C_ϵ^t . As can be seen, the solution is not very sensitive to either of these two parameters.

Figure 20: View of the solution of the KPP test at the segment line $x_1(s) = -1 + 2s/\sqrt{13}$, $x_2(s) = 1 - 3s/\sqrt{13}$, $0 \leq s \leq \sqrt{13}$ for $r = 4$ and $h/r = 0.00945$.

443 Furthermore, Fig. 21 shows the values of the discontinuity sensor S_K at the whole domain. As can be
 444 seen, for the case of CFL = 0.25, diffusion is mainly applied at the vicinities of the discontinuity. In contrast,
 445 when the CFL number increases, diffusion is also applied at the expansion waves and in other zones of the
 446 domain –although not in the same extent than in the shock– to maintain stability.

Figure 21: Values of the discontinuity sensor in the KPP test for $r = 4$, $h/r = 0.00945$ and $C_\epsilon^t = 3500$.

447 Finally, Table 1 shows the errors of mass –which is theoretically constant in the considered domain– for
 448 the cases represented in Fig. 20. As can be seen, those errors are not very dependent on the CFL number
 449 nor C_ϵ^t , due to the fact that the formulation is theoretically conservative irrespective of the value of these
 450 parameters.

Table 1: Mass errors of the KPP test for $r = 4$ and $h/r = 0.00945$.

	CFL = 0.25	CFL = 1.0	CFL = 1.75
$C_\epsilon^t = 3.5E+03$	1.0678E-07	2.5748E-08	6.9823E-08
$C_\epsilon^t = 1.0E+04$	1.3120E-07	1.6428E-08	4.7165E-08

3.5. Profiling times of the RK-FLG scheme

To analyze the efficiency of the RK-FLG scheme, we have run again Test III-a using different space discretization orders and mesh sizes. Then, we have measured the average per simulated instant of the total run-time, of the time spent computing the matrices of systems (11), (12) and (17), of the time spent on the search-locate algorithm for the computation of the right-hand side term in (17), and of the time spent solving systems (11), (12) and (17). Note that nine systems of equations must be solved per each simulated instant.

In all cases, systems (11), (12) and (17) are solved as follows. First, the system matrix is written as a 2×2 block matrix, whose blocks are related to the large-scale and to the fine-scale degrees of freedom. Since the submatrix related to the fine-scale terms is block diagonal, these terms can easily be condensed to provide a system written only in terms of the large-scale degrees of freedom. Then, the resulting system is solved via sparse Cholesky factorization. The simulations were performed in a six-core Intel i7-8750H CPU 2.20 GHz machine with 16 GB of RAM.

The profiling times are shown in Table 2. As can be seen, the computation of the system matrices is the most expensive task, followed by the search-locate algorithm and the resolution of the systems. The fastest times are obtained for third-order elements, followed by fourth-order, second-order and linear elements. It is seen that linear elements are clearly more expensive for the smallest value of h/r , which may be due to the fact that in this case the number of elements required is much higher than for the other discretization orders. On the other hand, fourth-order elements perform faster than second-order ones for ≈ 17000 nodes, and similar for ≈ 60000 nodes.

Table 2: Profiling times (in seconds) per simulated instant for the RK-FLG scheme.

r	h/r	Nodes	Elements	Total	System matrices in (11), (12), (17)	Search-locate algorithm for r.h.s. term in (17)	Resolution of systems (11), (12), (17)
1	0.0178	14725	29028	7.0482	3.1632	2.3705	0.3793
1	0.0094	52659	104520	33.5371	15.9797	10.3953	1.8877
2	0.0170	16193	7986	6.1169	2.3498	2.2234	0.8980
2	0.0089	58477	29028	12.2035	5.0376	3.6414	2.1255
3	0.0174	15535	3404	2.8294	1.1112	1.0105	0.4741
3	0.0091	55768	12302	9.9696	4.1156	3.0774	2.0412
4	0.0163	17721	2186	3.9188	1.7875	1.1657	0.7457
4	0.0085	64329	7986	12.0328	5.2938	3.5921	2.5144

To shed more light on this point, Fig. 22 shows the relation between the L^1 error and the total CPU time (t_{CPU}) for different space discretization orders. Here, we consider both Test III-a (whose solution is discontinuous) with $C_\epsilon^t = 1000$ and Test III-b (whose solution is continuous) with $C_\epsilon^t = 0$, and the experiments were performed in parallel in a 64-core AMD Epyc 7601 CPU 2.20 GHz machine with 28GB of RAM (one experiment per core). As can be seen, for discontinuous solutions, linear elements perform the slowest, whereas the rest of space discretizations perform similarly. For continuous solutions, however, performance improves with higher r as a consequence of the faster convergence rate.

Figure 22: L^1 errors of Test III-a (left) and Test III-b (right) versus CPU time (in seconds) for CFL = 0.5.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we present a novel (nearly) conservative, high-order, Lagrange–Galerkin method for the resolution of scalar hyperbolic conservation laws.

The method is based on a weak conservation law which can be formally discretized in time and in space with any order of accuracy, and from which the conservation equation for the standard mass can be seen as a particular case. The trajectories of the fluid particles are integrated forward in time to allow for more efficient and stable time discretizations. The scheme considers nodal space-discretizations on unstructured triangular meshes. Discontinuities are first detected by measuring the oscillations in a previously computed non-stabilized solution through the values of the fine-scale term, and are then captured via artificial diffusion.

The scheme has been tested on several benchmark problems –including the hard test by Kurganov et al. [67]– using up to fourth-order finite elements and a third-order time-marching formula. Numerical experiments show that the DC operator is able to capture the discontinuities with accuracy at the same time that it leaves unaffected the solution in the regions in which the latter is smooth. In general, $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$ and $\mathcal{O}(h/r)$ convergence rates in space are achieved for smooth and discontinuous solutions, respectively, whereas $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^3)$ convergence is achieved for the cases of prescribed velocity field and large enough Δt . Mass conservation is not fully achieved, but only with relative errors of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-7})$, although this could be alleviated by employing mesh intersection techniques [56–58].

To the best of our knowledge, the present method is the first conservative Lagrange–Galerkin algorithm that takes into account for nonlinear hyperbolic conservation laws and discontinuous solutions. Some works could be addressed in the future, such as to implement the above mentioned mesh intersection techniques [56–58], to enforce mass conservation with machine-precision accuracy via Lagrange multipliers [76], to perform a theoretical analysis of the error and of the stability of the method, to implement mesh adaptation strategies [18, 77] and to extend the method to the more complex case of the Euler equations of compressible gas dynamics.

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